

Challenges on polymer/cork composites for Rotomoulding applications

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Abstract:

Cork is a natural material exhibiting a closed cellular structure that confers to this material excellent properties such as light weight, impermeability to gases and liquids, thermal, electrical, sound and vibration insulation, fire resistance properties and exhibits a near zero Poisson coefficient. Cork and its by products are being used in many applications that favour eco design concepts, delivering aesthetics, comfort and functionality for many consumer products. The increasing demand for innovative and sustainable characteristics led to the study of polymer cork composites, since it is one of the most promising fields of cork technology. Different studies were carried to understand the mechanical, structural and thermal properties based on extrusion compounding and further injection moulding of the part. 1-4

In this particular study polymer cork composites have been studied for rotational moulding applications. No previous studies were found in literature on the use of cork materials in rotational moulding. This technique is used to produce hollow parts based on the rotation of polymeric powder material in an externally heated and cooled mould. Therefore, larger cycle times are involved comparing to other plastic processing techniques such as injection moulding or extrusion blow moulding used to process similar parts. Rotomoulding is a challenge for several materials due to the possibility of thermo oxidative degradation during processing. For these reasons there is the need for understanding the influence of the hybrid material composition and the processing conditions applied, on the aesthetics, morphological and mechanical characteristics of the parts.

Cork powder with different particle sizes ranging from 0,150 to 2/3 mm, provided by Amorim Cork Composites Portugal, were dry blended with MDPE (Rotolene 93050, MFI 5,2g/10 min @190°C/2,16 kg) in the proportions of 90/10, 85/15 and 80/20wt% and processed by rotational moulding. The processing cycle applied was the conventional for PE with a PIAT (peak internal air temperature inside the mould) of 210°C and 225°C and cooled by forced air. Good quality parts were obtained using fine cork powders (below 0,6 mm particle size). These parts are soft on touch and transmit the sensation of comfort and warm feeling of the cork. This cannot be achieved when using extrusion compounding, since the polymeric material imbibes the cork material resulting in a plasticslike touch. The colour of the part is very dependent on the processing temperature applied as depicted in Figure 1. The mechanical properties, evaluated by dart impact testing, are reduced considerably for PE/cork composites (2 J) as compared to a PE part (47J). As a result of voids being present in the structure, the microstructure created is not very compact, as observed in Figure 2. The increase of cork percentage results on the reduction of the sintering capability of the composite material increasing the porosity, wall thickness and surface defects simultaneously weakening the mechanical properties.

Cork material poses a challenge to rotational moulding since it may change its characteristics during processing as a result of high temperature and large cycle time applied. It is also difficult to produce a solid compact structure during the sintering process of the materials due to the free rotation of the mixed powders inside the mould. Currently, different strategies are being studied to improve the characteristics of the parts, namely the pressurization of the mould and an additional PE layer (bilayer part) to improve the mechanical properties, as it is shown in Figure 3. Combining the reduction of voids inside the part with an additional layer, an increment of mechanical proprieties is obtained (12J). This study is still in progress.

Keywords:

Rotational moulding, polyethylene, cork, morphological and mechanical properties.

Figure 1: Example of monolayer parts produced by PE/cork hybrid materials at different processing temperatures.

Figure 2: Example of the structure obtained for PE/cork hybrid materials at different compositions

Figure 3: Figure illustrating the bilayer structure of the rotomolded part composed of PE/cork at the outer layer and PE in the inner layer. On the right side it is represented the optical microscopy images of the bilayer structure, showing the details of its morphology. (Note that large voids are observed as a result of cork removal during the preparation of the sample for optical microscopy analyses).

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Structural Characterization of Zinc doped Hydroxyapatite Nanoparticles

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Abstract:

Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (HA np) have gained high scientific interest as a good candidate in diverse applications such as medical, agricultural, water purification and bio ceramics. The availability of many functional groups in HA allows it to be modified for various engineering applications. One such modification is the development of functional materials by doping HA np with different cations. In this study, Zn doped HA np were synthesized following a coprecipitation method. First, the method for synthesis of Zn doped HA np was established. A number of characterization techniques were used to study the structural features of Zn doped HA np. Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD) provided details about crystallinity and crystallographic features. PXRD results clearly indicated that parascholzite [CaZn₂(PO₄)₂(H₂O)₂] is formed and therefore suggested that some of the Ca ions have been isomorphously substituted by Zn ions during the reaction. Structural morphology was studied using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). A rod shaped morphology was observed for HA and Zn doped HA np. The interplanar distance of 211 plane obtained from TEM analysis demonstrated a shift from 0.27 nm to 0.29 nm upon Zn doping. This observation clearly indicated that there is a lattice distortion during the doping reaction. The functional group analysis was carried using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). FTIR study revealed that the crystallinity of HA decreases upon addition of Zn. Additionally, the observations from the X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) analysis revealed the presence of doublet bands at 346 eV and 350 eV, corresponding to Ca2p_{3/2} and Ca2p_{1/2} orbits, arising from two forms of calcium (Ca) ions in the composite. The two forms of Ca²⁺ can be labeled as the screw axis Ca ions and columnar Ca ions. In the Zn doped HA np, the core level spectra of Zn2p valence electrons split into two peaks at 1022 eV and 1045 eV which are attributed to Zn2p_{3/2} and Zn2p_{1/2} respectively, indicating divalent Zn ions are successfully doped into HA lattice.

The results suggest the successful synthesis of Zn doped HA Nano hybrids which are suitable for plant nutrient applications.

Keywords:

Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles, Zn doped hydroxyapatite nanoparticles, structural characterization.

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Vibrational and Thermal Properties of Ionic Conductors Type Pyrochlore H1-xAgxTaWO6.nH2O

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Abstract:

We have studied, by Raman spectroscopy, materials H1-xAgxTaWO6 and KTaWO6, both belonging to the pyrochlore system whose symmetry $Fd3m (Oh7)$. The experiments consisted in measurements of the Raman spectrum, at room temperature, on samples, before and after heat treatment. We have not performed photoinduced transformations studies on samples subjected to strong illumination. Instead of, we performed the heat treatment temperature of 700°C, where the transition phase takes place. Studies using the Group Theory were performed to describe the changes observed in the spectra as a function of heat treatment at different temperatures. During these studies, along with a comparison with information in the literature, it was possible to better understanding the thermal stability of the material. Our studies showing by both Raman spectroscopy and DSC/TG techniques there was not significant loss of mass. It means the samples may have performed transitions to defective pyrochlore phase AgTaWO6.

Keywords:

Group theory, Spatial group, Raman spectroscopy, Vibrational modes.

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Black seed oil incorporated polycaprolactone microspheres as an effective oil encapsulation approach

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Abstract:

The essential oil of the seeds of *Nigella sativa* (Black seed) has been used in traditional Arabic medicine to treat many diseases such as skin disorders, asthma, rheumatism, and headache. High volatility of essential oils can be an issue depending on the application. Controlled release of these oils, when desired, can be achieved via encapsulation in a polymeric material.

We envisioned to use uniaxial electrospinning to encapsulate black seed oil in polycaprolactone (PCL), which is one of the most extensively studied polymer due to its slow degradation and biocompatibility. Here, we report the successful encapsulation of black seed oil (BSO) in PCL microspheres using uniaxial electrospinning. PCL concentration (varied from 3 to 12% w/w) determined product morphology, fibers or spherical microspheres as seen under SEM. 7-12% w/w PCL yielded fibers while 3-5% w/w yielded microspheres. Interestingly, electro-spun composite of PCL/BSO yielded both microspheres and nano fibers with higher PCL concentrations of 10-12% w/w. The microspheres were cracked, aggregated and covered with fibers. With intention to obtain uniform, spherical morphology without fibers; PCL concentration was reduced from 12% w/w and the fibrous nature disappeared gradually resulting only aggregated microspheres at 3-5% w/w PCL concentration. Medium concentration of 79% w/w PCL was selected for further studies as it gave homogeneous microspheres embedded in a less dense nano fibrous structure.

This particular composite was further characterized using FTIR, TGA, UV-Vis and GCMS. FTIR analysis confirmed the incorporation of BSO in microspheres through weak interactions with the polymer. Thermal decomposition of all BSO, PCL and BSO/PCL occurs at around the same temperature range of 400-410 °C. The encapsulation efficiency and the loading capacity of the composite were calculated using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The release profile of BSO from BSO/PCL microspheres was studied using GCMS/Headspace analysis and the results indicated controlled release of BSO from the electro-spun spheres compared to the naked oil.

Keywords:

Electrospinning, Black seed oil, Polycaprolactone, BSO/PCL, encapsulation, controlled release.

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